

Effects of using the Informed Health Choices secondary school resources: protocol for a prospective meta-analysis

Protocol addendum

Oxman, AD, Mugisha M, Chesire F, Ssenyonga R, Rose CJ, Nsangi A, et al. IHC Working Paper, 12 June 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026599>

As noted in the protocol, we planned to assess potential adverse effects and use of what was learned in daily life (far transfer) in the one-year follow-up studies. Based on preliminary findings from interviews with teachers and students,¹ and user testing potential questions, we identified the following potential adverse effects that we will assess quantitatively: conflict due to students who participated in the lessons challenging the beliefs of others, stress, decision-making harms due to misunderstandings, and waste. Questions to assess these outcomes are included in questionnaires for students ([Appendix 1](#)) and teachers ([Appendix 2](#)). These questionnaires will be completed by participants in the intervention schools only ([Appendix 3](#)). The questions that address each of the potential adverse effects are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Questions about students and teachers experience with the “Be Smart about Your Health” lessons

	Questions	
	Students	Teachers
Waste	1-3	5-8
Conflict due to students challenging the beliefs of others	4-6	3
Stress	7	1-2
Decision-making harms due to misunderstandings		4
Other	8	

For each question, we will report the number and proportion of participants who selected each response options. For questions with three or more responses options, we will also dichotomise the responses (e.g., stressful or very stressful vs not at all stressful or a little stressful).

We will assess use of what was learned by asking students in both intervention and control schools to recall a claim about the effects of a health action using a “diary” ([Appendix 4](#) and [Appendix 5](#)). For each claim we will ask questions to assess their ability to identify and assess the claims and decide what to do.

We will randomly select 10 students from each school and code their responses as follows:

1. Was the action correctly identified?
 - A) Yes
 - B) No
2. Was the claimed effect correctly identified?
 - A) Yes
 - B) No

If either the action (1) or the claimed effect (2) was not correctly identified, stop here.

3. Was the basis for the claim correctly identified?

- A) There was not a basis for the claim
- B) Yes
- C) No

If the basis for the claim (3) is not correctly identified, stop here.

4. Was the assessment of the reliability of the claim correct?

If the basis is unreliable	If there was not a basis	If the basis is research		
		without information about the size of the study or whether groups were randomly created	and either the size of the study or whether groups were randomly created is noted	and both the size of the study and whether groups were randomly created is noted
A) Yes , if the answer is Unreliable	B) Yes , if the answer is Can't tell or Unreliable	D) Yes , if the answer is Can't tell	F) Yes , if the answer is Can't tell	I) Yes , if the answer is Reliable
B) No , if the answer is Can't tell or Reliable	C) No , if the answer is Reliable	E) No , if the answer is Reliable or Unreliable	G) No , if the answer is Unreliable	J) No , if the answer is Unreliable or Can't tell
			H) Partially , if the answer is Reliable	

In the answer to question 6:

5. Was the reliability of the claim considered?

- A) Yes
- B) No

6. Were the advantages considered?

- A) Yes
- B) No

7. Were the disadvantages considered?

- A) Yes
- B) No

8. Were any of the following considered?

- A) The student's personal experience
- B) What health professionals or researchers advise

Assuming 30% correct responses in control schools, 50% correct answers in intervention schools, 40 schools in each arm, 10 students per school, and an ICC of 0.2, using Strata, we estimate the power to detect this difference to be just under 94%. The primary outcome for these analyses is correctly assessing the reliability of the claim (question 4 above), and analysis is powered for this outcome. We will report effect estimates for the other outcomes listed above without correcting for multiplicity.²

We will use mixed models with a random effects term for the clusters and the stratification variables modelled as fixed effects, using generalised logistic regression to estimate odds ratios. To aid interpretation, we will re-express the odds ratio estimates as adjusted differences, accounting for uncertainty of the control odds as well as the odds ratios. Missing responses will be counted as incorrect.

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References

1. Oxman M, Chesire F, Mugisha M, Ssenyonga R, Ngatia B, Nsangi A, et al. Potential adverse effects of an educational intervention: Development of a framework. PLoS One. 2022;submitted. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.07.27.22278097>
2. European Medicines Agency. Adjustment of Significance and Confidence Levels. ICH Topic E 9: Statistical Principles for Clinical Trials. London: EMEA; 1998. p. 28. https://www.ema.europa.eu/documents/scientific-guideline/ich-e-9-statistical-principles-clinical-trials-step-5_en.pdf

Appendix 1: Adverse effects and transfer questions for intervention students

Questions about your experience with the “Be Smart about Your Health” lessons

Instructions

First, read the text above the questions and then answer each question on **the SCORE sheet**, using one of the provided answers.

For each question, choose what you think is the best answer and

fill in the circle for that answer in the score sheet **using a pencil**, like this.

If you want to change your answer, carefully erase the first circle that you filled in.

Do not fill in more than one circle for each question.

The examples below show you the one correct way and some wrong ways to mark your answers.

Be sure to fill in the circles the correct way.

Questions about you

1. Your school code

2. Your gender

Female

Male

3. Your age

Questions about your experience with the Be Smart about Your Health lessons

Below are some questions about what you think. **There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.**

1. *Question:*

Think about what you learned from these lessons. How helpful or unhelpful has that been to you?

Options:

- A) Very helpful to me
- B) Helpful to me
- C) Unhelpful to me
- D) Very unhelpful to me

2. *Question:* **Compared to what you learned in other subjects, how helpful has what you learned in these lessons been to you?**

Options:

- A) Less helpful
- B) About the same
- C) More helpful

3. *Question:* **How much have you used what you learned from the lessons?**

Options:

- A) Not at all
- B) A little
- C) A lot

4. Question: How much did you challenge things said by YOUR TEACHERS, based on what you learned in these lessons?

Options:

- A)** Not at all
- B)** A little
- C)** A lot

5. Question: If you challenged YOUR TEACHERS, how did this make you feel?

Options:

- A)** I did not challenge my teachers
- B)** Very bad
- C)** Bad
- D)** Neither bad nor good
- E)** Good
- F)** Very good

6. Question: How much did you challenge things said by YOUR PARENTS OR OTHER ADULTS AT HOME, based on what you learned in these lessons?

Options:

- A)** Not at all
- B)** A little
- C)** A lot

7. Question: If you challenged YOUR PARENTS OR OTHER ADULTS AT HOME, how did this make you feel?

Options:

- A)** I did not challenge my parents or other adults at home
- B)** Very bad
- C)** Bad
- D)** Neither bad nor good
- E)** Good
- F)** Very good

8. Question: How much did you challenge things said by OTHER STUDENTS OR FRIENDS, based on what you learned in the lessons?

Options:

- A)** Not at all
- B)** A little
- C)** A lot

9. Question: If you challenged OTHER STUDENTS OR FRIENDS, how did this make you feel?

Options:

- A)** I did not challenge other students or friends
- B)** Very bad
- C)** Bad
- D)** Neither bad nor good
- E)** Good
- F)** Very good

10. Question: How stressful were the lessons for you?

Options:

- A) Not at all stressful**
- B) A little stressful**
- C) Stressful**
- D) Very stressful**

11. Question: Did the lessons have any bad effects or disadvantages for you apart from stress or feeling bad about challenging what others said?

Options:

- A) Yes**
- B) No**

Appendix 2: Adverse effects and transfer questions for intervention teachers

Questions about your experience with the “Be Smart about Your Health” lessons

Instructions

First, read the text above the questions and then answer each question on **the SCORE sheet**, using one of the provided answers.

For each question, choose what you think is the best answer and **fill in the circle** for that answer in the score sheet **using a pencil**, like this.

If you want to change your answer, carefully erase the first circle that you filled in.

Do not fill in more than one circle for each question.

The examples below show you the one correct way and some wrong ways to mark your answers.

Be sure to fill in the circles the correct way.

1. How stressful was it for you to prepare and teach these lessons?

Options:

- A)** Not at all stressful
- B)** A little stressful
- C)** Stressful
- D)** Very stressful

If your answer to the first question was "A" (Not at all stressful), skip this question.

You can select more than one of these options.

2. Which of the following made the lessons stressful?

- A)** Taking time to prepare for the lessons
- B)** Taking time away from other subjects
- C)** Completing the lessons during the time available
- D)** Having to learn new material or methods
- E)** Getting off track because of students asking questions
- F)** Feeling unprepared to answer students' questions
- G)** Having students challenge things that I said
- H)** Teaching students who lacked motivation

3. How much did your students challenge (question) things that you said because of these lessons?

Options:

- A)** Not at all
- B)** A little
- C)** A lot

4. If they challenged things that you said, how did this make you feel?

Options:

- A)** They did not challenge things that I said
- B)** Very bad
- C)** Bad
- D)** Neither good nor bad
- E)** Good
- F)** Very good

5. Have you noticed your students using what they learned from the lessons?

Options:

- A) Not at all**
- B) Rarely**
- C) Sometimes**
- D) A lot**

6. Have you observed any of your students relying on any of the unreliable claims that were used as examples in the lessons?

Options:

- A) Not at all**
- B) Rarely**
- C) Sometimes**
- D) A lot**

7. Have you used what you learned from the lessons in your daily life?

Options:

- A) Not at all**
- B) Rarely**
- C) Sometimes**
- D) A lot**

8. Have you used what you learned from preparing and teaching the lessons in teaching other subjects?

Options:

- A) Not at all**
- B) Rarely**
- C) Sometimes**
- D) A lot**

9. To what extent would including these lessons in the national curriculum be advantageous or disadvantageous FOR STUDENTS?

Options:

- A)** The advantages far outweigh the disadvantages.
- B)** The advantages outweigh the disadvantages.
- C)** The disadvantages outweigh the advantages.
- D)** The disadvantages far outweigh the advantages.

10. To what extent would including these lessons in the national curriculum be advantageous or disadvantageous FOR TEACHERS?

Options:

- A)** The advantages far outweigh the disadvantages.
- B)** The advantages outweigh the disadvantages.
- C)** The disadvantages outweigh the advantages.
- D)** The disadvantages far outweigh the advantages.

Questions about your experience with the “Be Smart about Your Health” lessons

Instructions

1. These questions are for students in the intervention schools only.
2. Schedule additional time to explain these questions to the students and to give them time to answer the questions.
3. Explain that their answers will be used to evaluate how critical thinking about health is being taught, NOT to evaluate them. There are NO RIGHT OR WRONG ANSWERS.
4. Tell the students that they can ask you if there are any words or questions that they don't understand.
5. Make sure that they understand the word “challenge”. Explain that in these questions, it means to question something that is said, for example by saying that it is a claim, asking what the basis is, or saying that it has a weak basis or is unreliable.
6. Tell the students what the code is for the school on page 2, if this information is not already filled in.
7. Then give the students time to answer the questions.

Critical Thinking about Health

Definitions

Some words in this diary may not be familiar to you or may be used in a different way than you are used to.

HEALTH is how well someone's body and mind are.

A **HEALTH ACTION** is something that someone does to care for their health or the health of others.

An **EFFECT OF A HEALTH ACTION** is a change in health caused by the action.

A **CLAIM** is something that someone says as if it is true, but it may be wrong.

A **RELIABLE CLAIM** is a claim that can be trusted or relied on.

An **UNRELIABLE CLAIM** is a claim that cannot be trusted or relied on.

A **CLAIM ABOUT THE EFFECTS OF A HEALTH ACTION** is something that someone says as if it is true - but it may be wrong - about what will happen if you take a certain health action.

The **BASIS FOR A CLAIM** is the information used to support the claim.

What is TODAY'S DATE?

Questions about you

Please answer the following questions:

1. What is your school's code?

2. What is your gender?

Female

Male

3. What is your age?

Questions about the past week

Think about a **CLAIM ABOUT THE EFFECTS OF A HEALTH ACTION** that you heard, read, made, or thought about during the past week. **Then answer the questions on the next page.**

Here are some examples of claims about the effects of a health action:

- *A friend told me “After I put toothpaste on my pimples, the pimples went away. So, toothpaste removes pimples.”*
- *“Putting cow dung on a burn will heal the burn.” People have been doing that for a long time, so it must work.*
- *I heard “There is a new, expensive flu medicine that cures the flu.”*

Write **one** CLAIM that you, heard, read made, or thought about during the past week here. **DO NOT USE ONE OF THE CLAIMS ABOVE.**

For the CLAIM that you heard, read, made, or thought about:

1. What was the HEALTH ACTION in that claim? _____

2. What was the CLAIMED EFFECT in that claim? _____

3. Was there a BASIS FOR THAT CLAIM? Yes

No

If yes, what was it? _____

4. How reliable do you think that claim is?

Reliable

Can't tell

Unreliable

5. Would you take that health action, or would you advise someone else to take that health action?

Yes

No

6. If you answered YES, why would you?

If you answered NO, why wouldn't you?

Critical Thinking about Health

Instructions

1. Schedule 30 minutes to explain this exercise to the students and to give them time to answer the questions.
2. Explain that their answers will be used to evaluate how critical thinking about health is being taught, NOT to evaluate them.
3. After you collect their answers, you can use this as an opportunity to discuss critical thinking about health (using their answers as examples). This is optional, and you should schedule additional time for this.
4. Give the students time to read the definitions and for you to answer any questions that they have.
5. Emphasize that they should write just **one** claim and that it should be a claim that that they heard, read made, or thought about during the past week, **not** one of the examples.
6. Tell the students what the code is for the school on page 2, if this information is not already filled in.
7. Then give the students at least 15 minutes to write a claim on page 3 and answer the questions about the claim on page 4.